

JRP24-FBZSH9-BEONE D2.3

Workpackage 2

Responsible Partner: RIVM

Contributing partners: RIVM (30), INSA (36), SSI (13), PHE (22), NVI (33), RKI (11), APHA (21), PIWET (34)

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP – BeONE - Building integrative tools for OneHealth Surveillance
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	36 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Project deliverable	D-BeONE.2.3 Final Guidelines
Project Acronym	BeONE
Author	Claudia Coipan
Other contributors	Eve Fiskebeck
Due month of the report	M58
Actual submission month	M60
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 19-dec-22
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination <i>Author’s suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

FINAL GUIDELINES FOR CLUSTER DETECTION - SUMMARY

1. WGS – in a nutshell

1.1. Traditional surveillance

Surveillance of foodborne pathogens allows identification and control of outbreaks. Collection of good epidemiological information is essential for outbreak investigation and source finding, and the most detailed information is collected from the questionnaires the infected subjects are required to fill in. However, at the moment of the initiation of the outbreak investigations, this information is likely to be missing. It is in only exceptional instances of very well organized surveillance systems and mandatory notifiable diseases, that subjects are required to fill in a questionnaire at the moment of sampling and diagnostics. Furthermore, the differences in digital competences between age groups and/or social categories may limit the use of digital questionnaires. This extra time and qualified personnel to convert the analogue questionnaires into electronic data that can be readily analysed. Another obstacle in prompt usage of epidemiological data is the progressive nature of outbreaks, with slowly accumulating number of cases in the beginning, and therefore limited use of statistical tests for identifying common exposure variables.

1.2. WGS in surveillance

Whole-genome-sequencing (WGS) is being increasingly used as a routine typing tool for foodborne pathogens and it has revolutionized the field of molecular epidemiology. The benefits of WGS have been highlighted in many occasions [1–4] and include a much greater strain discrimination for bacterial typing, and the possibility to infer phenotypic information such as serovar, serotype, and antibiotic resistance patterns. This allowed an enhanced cluster resolution and an equally enhanced ability to detect clusters and to monitor disease trends.

Thus, when using a reference genome as a blueprint to deduce the isolate genome, the recovered genome is also a MODEL of the true genome of the pathogen.

2. Extracting information from millions of ACGTs – from genomes to profiles

2.1. Differences between genomes - different types of variants

The differences between closely related genomes can be classified in three different categories: structural variation, that result from genome reorganization, insertions and deletions (indels), and single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) [eg. olson2015?].

To our knowledge Genome reorganization is not currently employed to determine cluster for infectious diseases. However, it has been suggested that it might prove useful eg. in discriminating clusters of highly related isolate that would otherwise belong to an identical cluster (eg. [lindgren2019?]).

While some methods allow to detect indels, those are also rarely used in clustering

Most commonly used current algorithms to delineate cluster in infectious disease surveillance, are gene-by-gene methods eg. core/whole genome Multilocus Sequence Typing = cg/wg MLST, based on the detection of SNPs in a genome alignment.

These have been described in detail elsewhere [5] and we will resume ourselves here to the brief description of major categories.

2.2. cg/wgMLST

The more popular analytical approach for WGS typing is based on protein-encoding alleles, that are present in the “core genome” (cg) (often characterized as present in a high proportion of isolates, eg. 95%) or the whole genome (wg). This approach is designated as Multilocus Sequence Typing (cg/wgMLST).

2.3. SNPs

Another common analytical approach is SNP calling, which can be reference-free [8,9] or reference-based, with the latter being more common in practice.

2.4. Importance of the reference choice

The choice of an appropriate reference to detect SNPs is crucial [eg. pightling2015a?, reviews and other]. Reads originating from regions that are not found in the reference cannot map [5] or may map erroneously to another genomic region [valiente-mullor2021?], and can impact whether specific isolates are included or excluded within specific clades [valiente-mullor2021?].

2.4.1. Core vs whole genome ?

Any method relying on WGA will only allow to compare the portion of the genome that successfully aligned to each other.

2.4.2. Similar regions vs presence/absence

Some approaches that allow to bypass those limitations have been developed. Early attempts proposed the solution using graph based approaches, allowing mapping to multiple or to a population of reference genomes [schneeberger2009?]. Since, several related approaches have been developed (reviewed in [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8006571/>]). Even though they have the potential to provide greater information than currently used methods for cluster delineation they are not yet widely used for surveillance of infectious diseases.

2.5. Variant/SNP stability: calling algorithms

The local alignment of reads mapped to an existing reference may be imprecise, particularly in the presence of indels (eg ABRA2, which potentially may result in erroneous variant calls. It has been used in CLCbio (commercial: However, there is no general consensus of whether local realignment improves SNP calling [tian2016?], and therefore no consensus on whether this should be performed prior SNP calling.

Consequently, which SNPs are detected is not solely influenced by the reference choice, but also relies on the methods and software used to detect SNPs, as those react differently eg. for the different levels of divergence, their ability to handle indels. The quality filter employed also influence the ratio of True and false positive SNPs types.

2.5.1. Not all nucleotides contain the same information – unit of mutation

The identified SNPs are a representation of the point mutations that occurred during the evolution of a set of genomes since their most recent common ancestor.

Consequently, not all SNPs contain the same evolutionary information, thus different assumptions regarding to their mode of evolution, whether explicit or implicit, might lead to the obtention of different clusters.

3. Summarizing genomic profiles

Several distances measures, that are expected to represent the similarity or dissimilarity between genomes can be calculated.

3.1. Distance based

Several distances measures that allow to compare the similarity/dissimilarity among genomes can be used.

One has however to keep in mind that depending on genome coverage that is compared and of the characteristics of the measures itself. Eg if a “high similarity” (eg. 99.9%) discovered between genomes compared in around ca 10% of their genome coverage, does not preclude of discovering that with another measure that those genomes would be qualified as “dissimilar”.

3.2. Model-based

Model based distances measures are often used for SNPs analysis.

3.2.1. Characters

SNPs at each position of a multiple alignment are considered as characters with different states (A,T,C,G). Indels (-) can be in some cases considered as a 5th character state. However, in whole genome analyses, indels are often ignored in the analyses.

3.2.2. Interpreting the similarity – defining a cluster

Based on the distances between the isolates, clusters can be defined as subsets of isolates that have distances smaller than a predefined certain cut-off. Various thresholds have been defined for various pathogens, based on previous epidemiological experience.

4. Hierarchical clustering

4.1. Variations - different linkage methods

But can also use single-linkage clustering. What this method entails is, as the name suggests, finding a link between all isolates in a dataset, by using an agglomerative process. The process starts with two points in the dataset between which the distance is minimal across all possible pairs of points in the dataset. These are then linked together to form a first cluster. A next point in the dataset will be searched where the distance to this initial cluster is minimal. However, since in the initial cluster there are two points, a choice has to be made as to which distance to be used. The single-linkage method implies that the minimal distance will be chosen (by contrast, in average-linkage, the average of the distances will be taken, and in complete linkage, the maximum of the two will be taken). The distances resulting from such an algorithm are called phenetic distances.

4.2. Thresholds and methods to define them

4.2.1. Empirical

Distance-based clustering methods have been implemented in a number of software such as ClusterPicker [27] or SnapperDB [28]. Genetic distance cut-off values are useful tools for WGS cluster detection, but cannot be used by themselves to definitively exclude cases, as, often, they are restrictive e.g. for longer outbreaks there is a higher probability that the distances among the isolates will exceed the suggested threshold. In general, the decision on where to draw thresholds should be mindful of the specific agent (e.g., species, serotype) and its genetic diversity, ecology, and prevalence. An alternative to the use of cut-offs is to define a cluster

based on the data structure alone, where a cluster is a subset of isolates that have smaller distances among them than to other isolates.

4.2.2. Algorithmic

This alternative approach has the advantage of removing the necessity of defining empirically a threshold for each bacterial species and type of genetic data used, and it has been attempted increasingly more often in the past decade, either in the form of validity indices [29–31], bootstrap support values [32,33], or patristic distances [34]. All the nonparametric genetic clustering methods named above were well reviewed in [35]. These methods are mindless of the biology underlying the transmission processes. However, proper interpretation of genetic differences among the isolates requires knowledge of organism-specific biology and ecology and it has been suggested that model-based (parametric) clustering methods might outperform some of the nonparametric methods in recovering clusters.

Parameters -> “reliable” - dependent on strain - lineage - and knowledge might be lacking

The SNP variation is suitable for inferring evolutionary relations among the bacterial isolates, as nucleotides are the direct object of the mutational process. The most common source of genetic variation is mutation. The mutation rate, defined as the number of mutations per generation time, can be used in terms of “molecular clock” in order to refine the previously defined clusters. Thus, the incorporation of the time span between any two isolates and the expected mutation rate might act as prior knowledge in calculating the maximum possible distance observed among the isolates in the hypothesis of common descent.

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